

Title: How will Data will bring the future that we had envisioned.

Name: Prashant Kathuria

Affiliation: Swami Keshwanad Institute of Technology,Jaipur,India

INTRODUCTION:

Data is bringing revolution into fields like Healthcare,transportation,agriculture etc. How can we shape our tomorrow to a more positive perspective to bring the change we deserve. How the machines are learning to make our decisions and how can we proceed with it.

AIM:

To find a safe path with the right balance between the ethical future and the extent of automation in our lives.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

There have been a lot of recent advancements in the field of Healthcare. Trained machines have been claimed to perform better than experienced doctors. Testing those claims and focusing on whether the way they were performed was ethical as well. There have been claims of AI getting out of hand for humans and can prove risk worthy for many critical decisions which human were taking till date. To discuss these points and conclude on the path to take for the future will be discussed.

RESULTS:

We will observe the changes that have been there in our lives because of the recent advances in the Machine Learning field. And is this the path to proceed.

CONCLUSIONS:

We will be able to see how actually the recent advancements have affected out day to day living and how will be proceed from here as the right path to take for the future.

KEYWORDS:

Healthcare; Machine Learning; Artificial Intelligence;Data Science

BIOGRAPHY:

Prashant has been working on Machine Learning and Predictive Analytics from the past 3 Years, And has Developed and Delivered End-to-End usable products to be used and which are Helping big Pharmaceutical companies take better decisions and make choices through Data driven Technologies.